

Supplementary Material for RC-Map

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1 Additional Implementation Details

The conditional diffusion model is pretrained with a teacher–student setup. We freeze the LiDAR encoder in RC-Map as the teacher, and train a radar student with deterministic voxelization, a SpConv backbone, and a diffusion U-Net. The U-Net predicts noise conditioned on radar BEV features and learns to recover the frozen teacher’s LiDAR-like BEV representation. During RC-Map training and inference, LiDAR input is removed, and the trained diffusion module is fixed as a radar-side feature generator.

2 Camera 2D Lane Query Tokenization

As shown in Fig. 1, the detector uses the view-specific anchor bank to pool lane-level image features. For each candidate lane, we retain $M_{2d}=20$ sampled 2D point coordinates and pooled point-wise image features. The sampled 2D points are projected to ego-centric 3D locations by IPM. For point k on a lane, the point token is

$$h_k = f_k^{2d} + \text{PE}_{2d}(u_k) + \text{PE}_{3d}(P_{3D}(u_k)). \quad (1)$$

Inter-point self-attention then models ordered lane geometry:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_\ell = \text{SelfAttn}_{\text{point}}\left(\{h_k\}_{k=1}^{M_{2d}}\right). \quad (2)$$

The lane instance feature is augmented with camera identity and extrinsic information:

$$z_\ell = \text{Pool}(\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_\ell) + e_{\text{cam}(v)} + \text{MLP}(\text{vec}(T_{\text{ego} \leftarrow v})), \quad \tilde{z}_\ell = \text{SelfAttn}_{\text{lane}}(\{z_\ell\}). \quad (3)$$

During training, predicted 2D lanes are matched to projected 3D ground-truth map elements with an IoU-based assignment following LaneATT. During inference, the detector starts from the precomputed view-specific anchor banks, and NMS is used to suppress duplicate lane hypotheses.

3 Vectorized Decoder Details

The vector decoder contains $L=6$ stacked blocks. Each block iteratively refines query features and polyline anchors through point-wise self-attention, instance-level self-attention, cross-attention with fused BEV features, and a prediction

Fig. 1. Camera 2D lane query generation.

head. The point-wise operation captures local geometric interaction inside each polyline:

$$\hat{P}_i \leftarrow \text{SelfAttn}(P_i). \quad (4)$$

The instance-level operation allows lane, boundary, and crosswalk queries to interact:

$$q_i \leftarrow \text{SelfAttn}(q_i). \quad (5)$$

Finally, cross-attention injects scene context from the fused radar-camera BEV representation:

$$q_i \leftarrow \text{CrossAttn}(q_i, \mathbf{F}_{\text{fuse}}). \quad (6)$$

The updated query is decoded into semantic scores and refined polyline points, following the MapTR-style decoder paradigm.

4 Loss Details

We formulate online vectorized map construction as set prediction and supervise it with Hungarian matching. The instance-level loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{inst}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{cls}} + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{L1}} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{\text{dir}}, \quad (7)$$

and the point-level loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{point}} = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_j \|\hat{p}_j - p_j\|_1. \quad (8)$$

2D lane auxiliary loss. For each training sample, each BEV ground-truth map polyline is projected to camera view v and represented by normalized image points $\mathbf{U}_i^v = \{u_{i,k}^v\}_{k=1}^{M_{2d}}$ with a visibility mask $m_{i,k}^v \in \{0, 1\}$. Let candidate a predict score logit s_a^v and 2D points $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_a^v = \{\hat{u}_{a,k}^v\}_{k=1}^{M_{2d}}$. The direction-invariant matching cost is

$$C_{a,i}^v = \min_{r \in \{\text{fwd}, \text{rev}\}} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{M_{2d}} m_{i,k}^{v,r} \|\hat{u}_{a,k}^v - u_{i,k}^{v,r}\|_1}{\sum_{k=1}^{M_{2d}} m_{i,k}^{v,r} + \epsilon}. \quad (9)$$

Hungarian matching is performed independently in each view, and pairs with cost above τ_{2d} are discarded. The score loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{lane2d-score}} = \frac{1}{Z_s} \sum_{v,a} w_a^v \text{FL}(s_a^v, y_a^v), \quad (10)$$

where hard-negative mining keeps all positives and the highest-scoring negatives. The point loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{lane2d-pts}} = \frac{1}{Z_p} \sum_{(v,a,i) \in \mathcal{M}_{2d}} \sum_{k=1}^{M_{2d}} m_{i,k}^v \|\hat{u}_{a,k}^v - u_{i,k}^v\|_1. \quad (11)$$

The auxiliary objective and total training objective are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{lane2d}} &= \lambda_{2d\text{-score}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{lane2d-score}} + \lambda_{2d\text{-pts}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{lane2d-pts}}, \\ \mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} &= \mathcal{L}_{\text{inst}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{point}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{lane2d}}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

5 Additional Experiments

5.1 Effect of Diffusion Sampling Steps

Table 1. Ablation on the number of diffusion inference steps.

Steps	mAP \uparrow	FPS \uparrow
5	54.2	4.2
10	54.8	2.8
20	55.1	1.6

Increasing the number of sampling steps improves the approximation of the LiDAR-like structural prior, but the gain is modest compared with the latency increase. We therefore use 5 steps as the default setting.

5.2 Effect of 2D Lane Anchor Clusters

Table 2. Ablation on the number of K-means clusters used for view-specific 2D lane anchor banks.

Cluster Number	mAP \uparrow
64	54.2
96	55.7
180	56.1

Using 64 clusters gives limited coverage of projected lane-shape variations. Increasing the number to 96 improves query quality, while 180 clusters gives a smaller additional gain, suggesting diminishing returns once the anchor bank is sufficiently expressive.

5.3 Challenging Scenes

Table 3. Comparison between the pure-vision baseline and RC-Map on manually selected challenging scenes.

Scenario	Pure Vision	RC-Map
Night	32.7	40.9
Rain	33.5	39.3
Occlusion	35.8	41.0

RC-Map consistently improves over the pure-vision setting under low illumination, rain, and occlusion, indicating that radar helps preserve BEV geometry when visual observations are degraded.